

8T – Reasoning Three Generations & Particle Mixing

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October 23, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the general idea behind the framework of varying curvature, it is possible to present a reason for the question of three generations. That is by the type form of the primordial, which was presented in the beginning of the 8T thesis. The argument revolves around the coupling constant of the weak interaction, which states that there are exactly three Bosons which mediate the weak interaction. The author presents the mathematical formalism behind Fermion mixing, and makes a prediction concerning Bosonic mixing, using the weak interaction coupling term and an additional theorem which was postulated in order to expand and reason the scope of phenomena which is available in nature.

Introduction

The 8T has Bosons as net curvature on the manifold, which was invoked stationary. The setting of total curvature vanishing due to stationarity demand on the manifold to net curvature yielded the primordial series, which is describing the coupling magnitudes.

$$\left(2e^- * \prod_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i + e^-_{\mu} \right) + N_{V\mu} = 30,128,850,9254 \dots \quad (1)$$

The following form is the third from which represent the multiplier of the invariant scalar, eight, as a form representing the kind of "fields" each interaction has. The question at the heart of this paper is a result of a postulate the author will make just for this paper – the postulate: The Quark series is partly wrong. Suppose there exist only three generations and the pattern presented in, the 8T is partly wrong. The question is can this arbitrary number be reasoned using the primordial. Using the equivalence of matter, i.e. the Electron and the Boson of the weak interaction, it could be possible to reason that there exist exactly three generations, which is similar to stating there exist three kinds of Electrons.

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$$(8 \times 3 + (3)) + 3 = 30$$

$$(8 \times 3 + e^-_{\mu}) + W^-_{\mu} = 30$$

$$(3) = 3$$

$$e^-_{\mu} \equiv W^-_{\mu}$$

The key for the argument at the heart of this paper:

$$\Psi_i = 3$$

Which was used to describe the three kind of Bosons associated with the coupling of the weak interaction. Because of the isomorphism between the Electron and the weak interaction Boson, it is possible to claim there exist exactly three kinds of Electrons. Three kinds can be similar in a sense of color charge, that is differ within a specific generation, an idea which has no experimental validity as far as one knows. The second option is to claim it has a validity in terms of generation type, as with the two higher generation analogs, the Muon and the Tao it exactly three kinds of electron which differ in their mass, similar to how the Bosons of the weak interaction differ in their mass. If accepted we must require that the rest of spin one-half or matter, which belong to the Electron class, will have two higher analogs which differ in their mass. That is simpler and elegant solution to the enigma of three generation, which is utilizing the coupling constants series, and in particular the beautifully crafted weak interaction, which one used for the idea of SUSY and SEW unification, which revolves around aligning the net variations between interactions, using two nets from the third to the first:

$$8 + (1) + 2: [(8 \times 3) + (3)] + 3 : [(24 \times 5) + (3)] + 3$$

And the aligning will modify the point of intersection on the middle interaction:

$$(8 \times 3) + 2 = 26$$

The question of three generation is either an infinite series decreasing mass aspiring zero, which will allow the elimination of this arbitrary number of families. Or assuming this idea of Quark masses is wrong, there exist exactly three kinds of families as the multiplier of the weak interacting is identical to the Electron, and thus there exist three kinds of Electron which differ in their mass. This is a simpler solution than the Quark mass series, both in argument complexity and the length of description. The fact that the Bosons differ in their mass, means that different amounts of curvature is manifested in those numbers, it also applies to the Electrons, the more mass, the more curvature converging exist on that particle, since we mapped the Ricci curvature to energy, the more curvature converging, the more energy it has. That is by the arrow:

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

Since we mapped the Ricci curvature to energy, nature will aspire by the stationarity condition to the lowest state of curvature, i.e. energy, which is synonymous with a stationary manifold, which is flat. It also means that the lowest mass, i.e. curvature converging would be the most common, which is in essence a prediction. That prediction can be joined to the other predictions concerning type, which is the photon type:

$$(8 \times 3 \times 5 + e^-_{\mu}) + \gamma_{\mu}$$

$$\Psi_i = 5$$

Which lead to predicting a set of five distinct photons.

$$\mathcal{B} = \left\{ \left(\gamma^i_{\mu} \right); 1 \leq i \leq 5 \right\}$$

The subscript is the five-vector, the superscript the photon kind index. The question of three generation could be the hardest question in the history of Physics.

The answer must take the form of an infinite series, or an exact reason of this arbitrary number and no other. Comparing to The Quark series it is more elegant and simple as no manipulation was needed, where the Quark series was based on artificial manipulation, which makes the idea less elegant. So with the increase of sensitivity devices, if a four family at the ranges of masses will be ruled out, we can rely upon again the coupling series and the equivalences between the weak interaction Bosons and the Electron to explain why there are exactly three kinds of Electrons which differ in their mass. That is because there are only three Bosons mediating the Weak interaction. So all the universes because of the invariance of the prime ring, will possess three families of matter. But that is only explaining why there are only three families with decreasing masses, it does not provide the variational principle of those numbers, why those numbers were chosen in the first place.

One additional point is using the \mathcal{L} theorem, which states that nature generates extremums on objects and classes. So if we consider the families class, the Quark series require generating more objects than the solution suggested by the primordial. Using that idea the second solution is more likely.

$$(\Psi_i \equiv 3) \forall t$$

Where in the Quark series, the number aspiring infinity with time.

$$(\mathcal{f}_i^M \rightarrow \infty) \propto t$$

Where \mathcal{f}^M denote the family masses, while the subscripts run all over the families. It is given that:

$$\mathcal{f}_i^M > \Psi_i$$

The objects nature would aspire to generate is minima, those minimal objects apply across maximal range of other objects. Using the \mathcal{L} theorem it is clear that it has the edge. In addition, it is aligned with the current understanding of three Electrons which differ in their mass. Either way, this idea of type primordial should be examined on the set of photons as means of validating the prediction. It does not mean that the idea of the Quark series is completely wrong, as we still need a way to shift from one generation to the other, all it means is that the series should not exceed the third family. It is important to emphasize as the Quark series has provided among the most useful ideas which used all across the thesis, which is the $8 - (1)$ variations, indicating curvature converging as the cause of mass. Then with the proof of the primordial, when a mass is in a curvature ripple it cancels:

$$8 - (1) + 8 + (1) = 0$$

So, putting in concise manner, when one states that the Quark series is wrong, it means that the succession beyond the third family, which is the Up-Down Quarks does not exist. The idea of the $8 - (1)$ is still holding as true, and is given by the Jumps across the families using the invariant multiplier, seven. The new idea is imposing a restriction on the number of jumps which is possible, the validity is due to the equivalence of the Electron to the Boson of the Weak interaction.

Fermionic Mixing

In the 8T thesis, there exist a symmetry among the three generation, which is imposed by requiring the invariance of the actual coupling magnitudes. That is, the coupling are the same for all three generations.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e^-)] + \gamma$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma$$

Which result in the following relation:

$$(e^-) \equiv (\mu^-) \equiv (\tau^-) \equiv (3)$$

Now consider the following scalar divisor on each of those particles such that:

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\tau^-)}{3} \equiv (1)$$

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\tau^-)}{3}$$

Now take the combination of each of those:

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} + \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} + \frac{(\tau^-)}{3} = 3$$

Alternatively:

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} + \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} + \frac{(\tau^-)}{3} = (\tau^-) \cup (\mu^-) \cup (e^-)$$

That means each Fermion of each generation can be composed by a threefold combination of a three-generation Leptons. That the Tao in fact contains a mixture of Leptons. The combinations can take an infinite variety as long it sums to number of the original particle.

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} \equiv \frac{(\tau^-)}{3} \rightarrow (e^-)^D \equiv (\mu^-)^D \equiv (\tau^-)^D$$

The superscript meant for "divided" and for making the notation easier. Instead of writing those fractions of the integer three, each of the rescale standing for one. Now it is possible to take any fractions we would like, combine them as such that the summation will again reach the number of the original particle.

$$\frac{\mathcal{A}_1(e^-)^D}{K_1} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_2(\mu^-)^D}{K_2} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_3(\tau^-)^D}{K_3} = 3$$

Where multipliers and divisors are real scalars:

$$(\mathcal{A}_{1 \rightarrow n} \cap K_{1 \rightarrow n}) \in \mathbb{R}$$

However, is it legitimate to create such infinite mixtures, is another subject. The author will postulate another theorem, which will be coined as the V theorem. The letter chosen as it is the first in the word: Variety of Variation, the first as to express infinite mixing options, and the letter as it is the dominating mathematical and physical theme of the 8T.

The \mathcal{V} theorem – what is not excluded, will be physically manifested.

In other words, if nature does not forbid it, it is allowed and it will appear. Nature does not impose a restriction upon it, and that is a sufficient condition for the existence of phenomena. That theorem is important as it allows to make many predictions, without focusing on the question of "why". It is an elegant way to answer questions of the sort – "why there exist Quark mixing?". The answer is according to the theorem: **simply because it is not forbidden by nature**. Another point concerning the nature of mixing. Since the Electron contain much less mass and thus much less energy, we would expect that the Tao part would aspire zero in its combination. On the other hand, the Tao can be represented with a "fair share" of an Electron in its combination due its immense mass. Using that idea it is possible to add the mixing angles, which are results of trigonometric angles in such way that the combination will add up to the right number at the end. Since the Electron and its higher analogs are isomorphic to the Boson of the Weak interaction, the idea of particle mixing should be inherited to Bosonic class as well.

The difference is that Bosons vary according to type, while Fermions according to Generation. That is how the paper began. For the Weak interaction, there exist three distinct Bosons, which were synonymous with three Electrons of distinct kind to which we associate the idea of "Generation". That means that each Weak interaction Boson itself is a combination of the three Bosons, itself included.

$$\frac{\mathcal{A}_1(W^-)^D}{K_1} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_2(W^+)^D}{K_2} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_3(Z^0)^D}{K_3} = 3$$

$$\frac{\mathcal{A}_1(W^-)^D}{K_1} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_2(W^+)^D}{K_2} + \frac{\mathcal{A}_3(Z^0)^D}{K_3} = W^-$$

The result can be extended to any other interaction. As an example, it is possible to state that the photon kind is a mixture of five distinct photons, itself included and so on, When the fractions are summed, leading to the original kind photon. Nature does not forbid it, and thus it will appear. From bird's eye view, the only exclusion we have in the 8 theory is when trying to combine two Leptons, which leading to their vanishing and to the Photons propagated from nowhere, which is forbidden, also known as the Pauli exclusion.

The framework of the 8T is immensely rich in theoretical predictions due to the correlation of real numbers to particles, a feature of great beauty and simplicity. As an example, it is possible to predict that the Electron will be form as a combination of three Gluons.

$$\frac{(e^-)}{3} + \frac{(\mu^-)}{3} + \frac{(\tau^-)}{3} = 1 + 1 + 1 = 3$$

$$1 + 1 + 1 = e^-$$

And thus three Gluons, identical or distict would lead to:

$$1 + 1 + 1 = W^-$$

Elimination of Free Parameters

Equations (1.1) and (1.2) allows the elimination of the three gauge interactions free parameters. The standard model contains twenty-six of those parameters. Since the Quarks were theoretically predicted, in particular, two distinct elements that differ in sign, create nine threefold combinations and appear in even number. The author will argue that it is possible to eliminate or at least reduce the number of elements in that sector too. That is because of the following reason, since Quarks are two distinct elements, and we have eight gauge fields which mediate the strong interaction, i.e. operate in between those Quarks:

$$2^c = 8$$

$$c = 3$$

With the equivalence between the Boson of the Weak to the Electron it was predicted three Electron type particles to which we associate generation. That means analogs for matter particles. Overall summation

$$(\delta g_1, \delta g_2) \times 3 = 6$$

$$6c = 18$$

$$(e^-)^D \times 3 = 3$$

$$v_{e^-} \times 3 = 3$$

The coupling constants series, which the restriction allows us the count twenty four Fermions, with their anti-matter particles we reach forty eight. With the three interaction ,eight for the strong, three for the weak and the photon assumed at SM as one (8T predicted five), we reached almost the full standard model.

$$8 + 3 + 1 = 12$$

$$12 \times 2 = 24$$

Adding the anti-matter duals. Now adding the Higgs and the Graviton (SM -1, 8T-∞):

$$12 + 48 + 2 = 62$$

In the 8T the number of particles is infinite, given by the Primorial as each prime is not only a new interaction type, but also contain a versatile variants across that number range. That is, the given prime multiplier in real range of the scalar eight is the "type kind". For the next coupling, author will the coin the name as the Γ_μ Boson:

$$\mathcal{B} = \{(\Gamma_\mu^i); 1 \leq i \leq 7\}$$

So in that sense, the infinity is reached much rapid rate, as each interaction has indexed typed variants isomorphic to the magnitude of the prime. The infinity can also manifested in the number of Graviton compositions as was previously presented. So summing up, if we count those twelve free parameters out as it is possible to derive their existence from principle, (leaving out the question of the masses value), we have sixteen parameters less, twelve for the Fermion sector, three gauge interactions and one Graviton. The free parameters which left unaltered are the eight mixing angles and the Higgs free parameters. The parameters of Fermions are ruled out as we can derive them from principle (except masses), including the reason for three generation only.

Weak interaction Decay

Consider the decay between the following pairs:

$$e^-e^+ \rightarrow W^-W^+$$

It is possible to expand using the primordial would be the question of this article.

$$e^-e^+ \rightarrow (3 + (-3)) = 0$$

Which is similar to the Boson of the weak interaction. It is possible than to correlate the e^+ to the W^+ which is in agreement with the fact that their charges are the same. The release of energy takes the form of the Bosonic pair, as it was Energy was mapped to curvature, and the Bosons are net curvature diverging.

$$\varphi: g \rightarrow E$$

The amount of energy released can be correlated to the total sum represented by their number:

$$|e^-e^+| = +(6)$$

And therefore, so does the resulting pair.

$$W^-W^+ = +6$$

Since the W^-W^+ pair is isomorphic to the $|e^-e^+|$ pair, which vanish into zero, it is possible to state:

$$W^-W^+ = 0$$

Which is similar to how matter is formed given by the main equation arbitrary variation term:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

Which means that the Boson pair could decay into matter. That is that matter of certain sort, whether it is Lepton or Hadron components may rise as a result of the:

$$W^-W^+ = 0$$

It is the only interaction in which the thing is currently possible as the photon was not found to have an anti-matter particle distinct from itself, and the Boson of the strong interaction is confined in the hadron components, which are bound states of the Quark formation. So using that decay alongside the equivalence of those elements, the e^- and the W^- it is possible to explain the range of the decay of the weak interaction. This can be described using the theorem, if one process is allowed, so does the inverse process is:

$$W^-W^+ \rightarrow e^-e^+$$

Using the V theorem, if it is not forbidden it will appear. It is possible to make another prediction without the Weak interaction Bosons, but only with the Electron Positron pair.

$$e^-e^+ \rightarrow \delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2$$

It is possible to predict that in more general form:

$$[M][AM] \rightarrow (\delta g_i \delta g_j \delta g_k)^A + (\delta g_j \delta g_i \delta g_j)^B$$

Where $[M][AM]$ denote matter anti matter pair, and the indexing on the right side can take any two values:

$$(i, j, k) \in (1 \cup 2)$$

If:

$$(i \equiv j) = Val_1 \in A$$

Than:

$$j \equiv k = Val_1 \in A$$

And:

$$((i \equiv j) = Val_2) \in B$$

$$Val_1 \neq Val_2$$

Else if:

$$(i \neq j) \in A$$

Than:

$$(k \equiv i) \cup (k \equiv j) \in A$$

While:

$$((k \equiv i) = Val_1) \in A$$

Do:

$$((j \neq i) = Val_2) \in B$$

While:

$$((k \equiv i) = Val_2) \in A$$

Do:

$$((j \neq i) = Val_1) \in B$$

The result of the algorithm is that Lepton pair can form matter configuration in which curvature is not allowed. It is possible to present the idea in a simpler fashion without the conditionals and the indexing. Simply stating that the Lepton pair and matter anti-matter pair will end up being identical.

$$e^- e^+ \rightarrow [M][AM]$$

$$[M][AM] = \{q\bar{q}\}$$

Manifolds Parity

Consider the main equation of the 8T using the manifold packet form:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n = 0$$

$$1 \leq m, n < k/2$$

It is possible to map the following manifolds to inverse signs of spatial dimensions, i.e. curvature orientations such that:

$$s_m = (M_E, g) \rightarrow (+)$$

$$s_n = (M_E, g) \rightarrow (-)$$

The main equation will be the same under parity transformation, i.e. transformation of the spatial while retaining the temporal:

$$s_m = (M_E, g) \rightarrow (-)$$

$$s_n = (M_E, g) \rightarrow (+)$$

Leading to:

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_n}{\partial t_n} \delta g_n - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M_E} \frac{\partial M_E}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g_m}{\partial t_m} \delta g_m = 0$$

Which is another way to state that those manifolds are topologically invariant. That is that the curvatures on the manifolds, are identical and flat each other out assumed perfectly. Thus if changing the signs of the manifolds it makes no difference, and the main equation obey the parity transformation, which is represented in Quantum theories using:

$$\Psi(x, t) \rightarrow \Psi(-x, t)$$

Hadron Formations

Using the main equation, the formation of atoms was presented as the following set:

$$(\delta g_3 \delta g_3 \delta g_3)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_2) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1)$$

$$(\delta g_1 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

It recently became evident to one, that there could be different stages in the formations of Hadrons: that is, they can be variants of the form:

$$\delta g_2 \delta g_2$$

Leading to attachment to the inverse variants:

$$\delta g_1 \delta g_1$$

Such that the hadron will contain an even number of arbitrary variation, leading to zero curvature overall. Partitioning:

$$(\delta g_1 + \delta g_1) + (\delta g_2 + \delta g_2) = 0$$

So the Hadron will be presented as an even formations of Quarks.

$$\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1$$

Using the V theorem, it is not forbidden so it will be allowed and it will appear in nature. There could be such states in which the hadron is formed in stages.

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2) + \delta g_1 \rightarrow (\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1)$$

Which will pair to the inverse:

$$(\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1) \leftrightarrow (\delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_2)$$

Such that the stationarity condition will hold true. As one is not a particle physicist, those combinations may already have definite names and have already been discovered. The point of this section is to expand the theoretical range of matter formations given by the main equation. The same equation which yielded the primordial. Theoretically it is possible to expand the result to any number. As an example take the scalar multiple:

$$2 \times \delta g_2 \delta g_2 = \delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2$$

Which will pair:

$$2 \times \delta g_1 \delta g_1 = \delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1$$

Leading to eightfold formations in the hadron.

$$\delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_2 \delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1 \delta g_1$$

The probability of this however is aspiring zero as we require perfect alignment of two distinct elements again and again, that is three transformations from an element to itself in succession to each kind.

$$\delta g_2(e) \delta g_2(e) \delta g_2(e) \delta g_2 \delta g_1(e) \delta g_1(e) \delta g_1(e) \delta g_1$$

"e" Denote the natural transformation of group theory. So the probability of creation is inversely proportional to the number of times we require a specific operator:

$$\leftrightarrow = \{e, O, Y\}$$

Which denote the set of operators, which currently contains three distinct maps between those varying elements, so the chance of one appearing is than smaller than one:

$$P_e < 1$$

Thus the chance for an eightfold formation is aspiring zero with the increase of index count, i :

$$\sum_{i=1}^6 (P_e)_i \rightarrow 0$$

Weak Interaction Photon coupling

Given by the isomorphism of the Electron to the Boson of the Weak interaction given by the Weak coupling term, it is possible to predict that the interaction between the Photon and the Electron should be identical to the photon and the W^- Boson interaction. Put another way, the Photon should couple to the W^- exactly as it couples to the e^- .

$$[(8 \times 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$3 = (3)$$

Higgs Fields

Given by first coupling term, which used to describe the type of Gluons, it is possible to make another prediction according to spin form of the primorial. That is that the first coupling term, which is correlated to spin zero by the classification:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Examining the first term of the coupling and comparing with the spin classification:

$$2N_0 = 2^{e^-} = 8$$

It is possible to predict using the type form of the primorial that there will be just eight types of spin zero particles, i.e. Higgs fields. That is in contrast to the prediction of the infinite Higgs field as presented in earlier stages of the thesis. It is currently unclear how does the Higgs itself is getting its mass.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

M. Ohad's Theory